

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND
TECHNOLOGY MUKKA, MANGALURU, KARNATAKA- 574146

DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL ENGINEERING

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project work entitled "**EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF FLY ASH, M-SAND AND GGBS WITH CONCRETE**" has been carried out by Mr. HITHESH (ISU18CV006), MOHAMMED RAHIF (ISU18CV010), MOHAMMED BAZIL (ISU17CV018) & ARJUN R (ISU18CV002) bonafide students of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY MUKKA in partial fulfilment for the award of "Bachelor of Technology" in "Civil Engineering" of the Srinivas University, Mukka during the year 2021-2022. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the Department of library. The project report has been approved and satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde
(Project Guide)

Prof. Shrinath Rao K
(Project Co-ordinator)

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde
(Head of the Department)

Dr. Thomas Pinto
(Dean)

External Viva-Voce

Name of the Examiners

1. HANBASHREE
2. _____

Signature with date

7/7/22

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND
TECHNOLOGY MUKKA, MANGALURU, KARNATAKA- 574 146**

DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL ENGINEERING

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project work entitled "BAMBOO REINFORCEMENT IN LATERITE CONCRETE" has been completed by CHARANSAI PASHIKANTI(1SU19CV704), SURAJ KUMAR BADUGU(1SU19CV701), D.BASAVA REDDY(1SU19CV702), ABHIN TV(1SU18CV001) under the guidance of Mr. PRASANNA P RAO, ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, and under the co-guidance of Mrs. J.D AKSHATHA, RESEARCH SCHOLAR, department of Civil Engineering, Srinivas University, Mukka, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Bachelor of Technology in Civil Engineering of Srinivas University, and no part of it has been submitted for the award of a degree or diploma in any university or institution previously.

Mr. Prasanna P Rao

Project Guide

Dept. of Civil Engineering

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde

Head of the department

Dept of Civil Engineering

Mr. Shrinath Rao K

Project Co-ordinator

Dept. of Civil Engineering

Dr. Thomas Pinto

Dean

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

1. HAMSASHREE

2. _____

Signature with date

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, MANGALURU, KARNATAKA- 574 146

DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL ENGINEERING

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project work entitled "**IMPLEMENTATION OF WASTE TYRE CRUMB IN CONCRETE INTERLOCKS**" has been carried out by **CHANDAN K (ISUI8CV003) SHIVARAJ PATIL (ISUI9CV705) KEERTHIRAJ REDDY K P (ISUI8CV008) MANIKANTA H (ISUI8CV009)** bonafide student of **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY** in partial fulfillment of requirements for the award of the degree of **Bachelor of Technology in Civil Engineering** of the **Srinivas University, Mangaluru** during the year **2021-2022**. It's certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the departmental library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Mr. Prasadanna P Rao

Project Guide

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde

Head of the Department

Mr. Shrinath Rao K

Project Coordinator

Dr. Thomas Pinto

Dean

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

1. HAMSASHEER
2. _____

Signature with date

7/12

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, KARNATAKA- 574 146

DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL ENGINEERING

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project work entitled “**COMPARSION ON ANALYSIS OF SHEAR WALL FOR A BUILDING USING STAAD PRO AND ETABS**” has been carried out by “**HARSHITH (1SU18CV005), NISCHAY B L (1SU18CV012), ENOSH A DOMELLO (1SU18CV004), HUSAIN JUNAIDH (1SU18CV007)**” bonafide student of **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY** in partial fulfillment of requirements for the award of the degree of **Bachelor of Technology in Civil Engineering** of the Srinivas University, Mangaluru during the year **2021-2022**. It's certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the departmental library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Mrs. Shilpa S

Project Guide

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde

Head of the Department

Mr. Shrinath Rao K

Project Coordinator

Dr. Thomas Pinto

Dean

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

1. HAMSASHREE

2. Shrinath Rao K.

Signature with date

7/7/22

07/07/2022

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY**

MUKKA, SURATHKAL, MANGALORE – 574146

Department of Civil Engineering

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled ***"EVALUATION OF THE PROPERTIES OF CONCRETE WITH WASTE PLASTIC POWDER"*** is a bonafide work carried out by Ms. SUDHA S. bearing the USN 1SU18CV027 in the partial fulfilment for the award of **Bachelor of Technology in Civil Engineering** of the Srinivas University, Institute of Engineering & Technology during the year 2021-22. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the department library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

K. Shrinath Rao

Mr. Shrinath Rao K

(Project Coordinator)

Dr. Ramakrishna Hedge

Dr. Ramakrishna Hedge

(Project Guide and HOD)

28/05/22

Dr. Thomas Pinto

(Dean, SUIET, Mukka)

External Viva

Name of the Examiners

Signature with date

1. HAMSASHREE

Hamsashree
7/5/22

2. _____

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, MANGALURU, KARNATAKA - 574146

DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL ENGINEERING

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project work entitled "**PARTIAL REPLACEMENT OF CEMENT USING BAGASSE ASH IN CELLULAR LIGHTWEIGHT CONCRETE BLOCK**" has been carried out by **Sinchana L G (ISU18CV024)**, **Sangamesh H N (ISU18CV022)**, **Suban samad (ISU19CV707)**, **Pooja gowda G L (ISU18CV013)** bonafide students of **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY** in partial fulfilment of requirements for the award of the degree of **Bachelor of Technology** in **Civil Engineering** of the **Srinivas University, Mangaluru** during the year 2021-2022. It's certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the departmental library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

.....
Mrs. Shilpa S
(Project Guide)

.....
Prof. Shrinath Rao K.
(Project Coordinator)

.....
Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde
(Head of Department)

.....
Dr. Thomas Pinto
(Dean)

External Viva-Voce

Name of the Examiners

1. HAMSASHREE
2. Shrinath Rao K.

Signature with Date

2. Sangamesh
7/1/22
- K. Shrinath Rao.
07/01/2022.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, MANGALURU, KARNATAKA - 574 146

DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL ENGINEERING

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project work entitled **"PREPARATION OF MASTER PLAN FOR MOODABIDRE TOWN:2022-2032"** has been carried out by Rathik R Nayak (ISU18CV019), Prasad G Devadiga (ISU18CV014), Delson Dsouza (ISU18CV023), Ria Krishna (ISU18CV020) bonafide students of SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY in partial fulfilment of requirements for the award of the degree of **Bachelor of Technology in Civil Engineering** of the Srinivas University, Mangaluru during the year 2021-2022. It's certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the departmental library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

Prof. Shrinath Rao K.
(Project Guide)

Prof. Shrinath Rao K.
(Project Coordinator)

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde
(Head of Department)

Dr. Thomas Pinto
(Dean)

External Viva-Voce

Name of the Examiners

1. HAMSASHREE

Signature with Date

2. Hamsashree
7/2/22

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY MUKKA,
SURATHKAL, MANGALORE-574146

CERTIFICATE

The is to certify that the Project entiled "An Experimental Study On Strength Evaluation Of Concrete Using Red Mud", is carried out by Ms. Deeksha.U bearing(USN: 1SU19CV703),Rajesh Nayak(1SU18CV017),Siraj(1SU19CV706) Priyanka H.B (1SU18CV015).Under the Guidance of Dheekshith.K,Assistant Proffessor,Department of Civil Engineering.SUIET,Mukka.In partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Bachelor of Technology in Civil Engineering, and no part of it has been submitted for the degree or diploma in any University or Institution previously.

Mr.Dheekshith.K

Guide, Assistant professor
Dept. of Civil Engineering

Mr.Shrinath Rao.K

Project Co-Ordinator
Dept. of Civil Engineering

Dr. RAMAKRISHNA HEDGE

Head of the Department
Dept. Of Civil Engineering

Dr.Thomas.Pinto

Dean

Name of the Examiners

1. HAMBASH H REDD
2.

Signature with Date

7/2/21

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
MUKKA, MANGALURU, KARNATAKA - 574 146

DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL ENGINEERING

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project work entitled **“AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF GROUND WATER QUALITY ANALYSIS NEAR PACCHANADI DUMPING YARD, MANGALURU”** has been carried out by **Rishith. D. S (1SU18CV021), Thanya Girish (1SU18CV030), Preksha P (1SU18CV029), Rakshith (1SU18CV018)** bonafide students of **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY** in partial fulfilment of requirements for the award of the degree of **Bachelor of Technology in Civil Engineering** of the **Srinivas University, Mangaluru** during the year 2021-2022. It's certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal assessment have been incorporated in the report deposited in the departmental library. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of project work prescribed for the said degree.

K. Shrinath Rao.

Prof. Shrinath Rao K.
(Project Guide)

[Signature]

Dr. Ramakrishna Hegde
(Head of the Department)

K. Shrinath Rao.

Prof. Shrinath Rao K.
(Project Coordinator)

[Signature] 26/10/22

Dr. Thomas Pinto
(Dean)

External Viva-Voce

Name of the Examiners

1. Hamsashree

Signature with Date

2. Hamsashree 26/10/22